

Experimental and Numerical Investigation of the Centre Cracked Horseshoe Disc Method for Determining the Mode I Fracture Toughness of Rock-like Material

Abstract

This paper presents a new procedure for determining the fracture toughness of rock-like specimens using the diametric compression test with the centre cracked horseshoe disc (CCHD) method. Using finite element analysis, a dimensionless stress intensity factor was obtained and a formula was rendered for determining mode I fracture toughness. To evaluate the accuracy of the measurement results produced by the CCHD method, fracture toughness experiments were conducted on the same rock-like material using the notched Brazilian disk (NBD) method. The CCHD tests were simulated using a two-dimensional particle flow code for validation of the experimental results and a great agreement between the pattern of crack initiation and propagation between the experimental and numerical simulations was observed. Lower values of fracture toughness were obtained from CCHD experiments than NBD tests due to purely tensile stress distribution at the tip of the existing notch in CCHD method.

Keyword: Fracture Toughness, Stress Intensity Factor, Centre Cracked Horseshoe Disc, PFC2D

1. Introduction

Rock fracture mechanics is applied in engineering problems related to rock breakage, including tunnel boring, rock drilling, hydraulic fracturing, and oil exploration (Anderson 2005). A material's fracture toughness represents the ability of the material to resist crack initiation and propagation. The mode I fracture toughness, K_{IC}, is commonly used for evaluation of fractures in materials including rocks. Various testing methods with different specimen geometries have been developed for measuring mode I fracture toughness (Dai et al. 2015a). Rock specimens in fracture toughness tests are typically core-based and can be categorized into three groups based on their sampling shapes: cylindrical configurations (group I), disc configurations (group II) and half-disc configurations (group III). Group I includes the straight edge cracked round bar bend (SECRBB) method (Ouchterlony 1982) and two methods suggested by the International Society for Rock Mechanics (ISRM) for testing this group of materials (Ouchterlony 1988): chevron bending (CB) and short rod (SR). These methods require access to long and intact rock cores (Cui et al. 2010). Also, the complexity of the equipment setup and the requirements of the testing apparatus (Fowell and Chen 1990; Lim et al. 1994; Chang et al. 2002) discourage the widespread adoption of those methods in general. For the short rod method, in particular, the tensile load needs to be applied perpendicular to the prefabricated chevron notch, which can be considered as a constraint in testing that can potentially reduce the chance of producing consistent toughness values for the same material. The ISRM-suggested methods improved the consistency of the values, but there is generally a 20-30% variation in toughness values reported and observed in the CB and SR test values (Iqbal and Mohanty, 2007).

Group II, which is specimen geometry based on disk shapes, is the focus of many methods including the Brazilian disc (BD) method (Guo et al. 1993); the cracked straight through Brazilian disc (CSTBD) method (Awaji and Sato 1978, Atkinson et al. 1982, Aliha et al. 2010, 2012a, b); the double-edge cracked Brazilian disc (DECBD) method (Chen et al. 2008); the

flattened Brazilian disc (FBD) method (Wang and Xing 1999, Keles and Tutluoglu 2011); the hollow centre cracked disc (HCCD) method (Amrollahi et al. 2011); the holed-cracked flattened Brazilian disc (HCFBD) method (Tang et al. 1996); the holed-flattened Brazilian disc (HFBD) method (Yang et al. 1997); the modified ring (MR) method (Thiercelin and Roegiers 1986, Thiercelin 1989, Tutluoglu and Keles 2011); the radial cracked rig method (Shiryaev and Kotkis 1982); and the ISRM-suggested cracked chevron notched Brazilian disc (CCNBD) method (Wang et al. 2003, Iqbal and Mohanty 2007, Dai et al. 2010a, 2015a). Among these methods, the CCNBD method is most frequently used due to its ease of sample preparation, simple testing procedure, low data scatter (Dwivedi et al. 2000, Nasserri et al. 2006); larger tolerance to specimen machining errors in the samples used (Dwivedi et al. 2000); wide-ranging specimen geometries and low required amount of intact core material (Iqbal and Mohanty 2007); and the availability of pure mode II or mixed-mode (mode I and mode II) fracture studies (Fowell et al. 2006, Xu et al. 2015). The schematic view and the configuration of the testing are shown in Fig. 1a for the CCNBD test.

In a circular disk with a central vertical straight notch ($\beta=0$) subjected to a diametrical compression load (Fig 1a), the tensile cracks propagate from the notch tip. In this condition, the following mathematical expression, proposed by Atkinson et al. (1982), can be used for mode I fracture toughness calculation:

$$K_{IC} = \frac{P\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{\pi RB}} N_I \quad (1)$$

$$N_I = 1 - 4\sin^2 \beta + 4\sin^2 \beta * (1 - 4\cos^2 \beta)(a/R)^2 \quad (2)$$

Where K_{IC} is the mode I fracture toughness; R is the radius of the Brazilian disk; B is the thickness of the disk; P is the compressive load at failure; a is the half-crack length; and N_I is the non-dimensional coefficient which depends on a/R and the orientation angle, β .

The test methods conducted on half-disk geometries (Group III) include the notched semi-circular bend (NSCB) method (Dai et al. 2010b, Zhou et al. 2012, Dai and Xia 2013, Kuruppu et al. 2014) and the cracked chevron notched semi-circular bend (CCNSCB) method (Kuruppu 1998, Chang et al. 2002, Dai et al. 2011, Zhou et al. 2012, Ayatollahi and Alborzi 2013, Wei et al. 2015, Xu et al. 2015). These half-disk specimens have the advantage of simpler preparation and loading than the other two groups. Note that these semi-circular bending (SCB) type methods are also suitable for mixed mode fracture studies (Kuruppu and Chong 2012). The notched semi-circular bend method has been widely used by researchers and was recently accepted as an ISRM-suggested method for measuring the mode I fracture toughness of rock (Zhou et al. 2012, Kuruppu et al. 2014). The CCNSCB method was proposed by Kuruppu (1998) and combines the superior features of the CCNBD (Fowell 1994) and NSCB (Zhou et al. 2012, Kuruppu et al. 2014) methods, and also overcomes some weaknesses of the two ISRM-suggested methods (Dai et al. 2015b). The CCNSCB specimen can be regarded as half-CCNBD so it inherently removes the symmetrical crack propagation assumption of the CCNBD method. The chevron notched SCB specimen avoids the difficulty of pre-cracking a sharp crack required in the NSCB method (Suresh et al. 1987, Bergmann and Vehoff 1994). In reality, pre-cracking is tedious to perform on rock materials. Interestingly, a novel chevron notch in CCNSCB can induce self-pre-cracking during testing and lead to stable crack propagation when the peak load is reached (Chang et al. 2002). Although it has many inherent merits, the CCNSCB method has not been as popular as the NSCB method due to the limited amount of data available on the dimensionless stress intensity factor (SIF) of CCNSCB specimens. A few researchers have calculated the SIF values on selected CCNSCB specimen

geometries. Ayatollahi and Alborzi (2013) calculated the SIF values using a slice synthesis method (SSM).

The difficulties of the abovementioned techniques can be overcome by conducting compression tests on the centre cracked horseshoe disc (CCHD) (Fig 1b). Both experimental and numerical experiments were conducted utilizing the CCHD method for mode I fracture toughness measurements of rock-like materials. The rock-like material has been extensively used as a model material for soft rock (Einstein and Hirschfeld 1970, Reyes and Einstein 1991, Shen et al. 1995, Bobet and Einstein 1998, Mutlu and Bobet 2006, Hedayat et al. 2014a, 2014b, 2014c, Hedayat and Walton 2017) and has the advantage that it can be made accurately, timely and economically.

The finite element method was utilized to calculate the dimensionless SIFs of wide ranging CCHD geometries. To evaluate the accuracy of the measurement results produced by the CCHD method, the fracture toughness experiments were conducted on the same material using the NBD method (ISRM 2007). Finally, the CCHD test was simulated in PFC2D to validate the experimental results.

2. Centre Cracked Horseshoe Disc (CCHD) Method

The CCHD method utilizes a horseshoe-shaped disc with a radius of R_e in which a central hole with a radius of R_i is drilled. One straight central crack with the length of b is created from the surface of the hole. The vertical force is applied to the sample by using two flat and wedge loading walls (Fig 1b).

Fig 1. (a) Notched Brazilian disk specimen under diametrical compression (modified from Atkinson et al. (1982)); (b) Centre cracked horseshoe disc.

2.1. Test specimen

Three mixtures of rock-like specimens with different tensile strengths were prepared. The specifications of their mixture ratios and physical/mechanical properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Specification of mixture ratio and their physical/mechanical properties.

Sample Types	Sample Mixture	Materials Ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Wave Velocity (m/s)	Uniaxial Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
1	Cement/grain/water	1/0.5/1	2900	3500	27.7	2.9

2	Cement/grain/water	0.5/0.5/1	2650	3075	19.2	1.6
3	gypsum/water	0.5/1	2400	2765	7	0.9

The mixing, casting, and curing of the specimens were carefully controlled to obtain reproducible specimens with precise properties. Mixing the material constituents was carried out with a blender. The mixed material was cast in a special mold for sampling rock-like discs (Fig 2a). The external part of the mold consisted of two semi-cone cylinders 90 mm in diameter and 27 mm thick. These cylinders were bolted to each other with an elastic band. The internal part consisted of one small cylinder, one semi-cone, and one thin blade attached together. The diameter of the internal cylinder was 20 mm and the length of the blade was 9 mm (Fig 2a). The angle of the cone walls attached to the cylinder was 14° and their thickness was 27 mm. A small pin was used to attach the internal and external parts (Fig 2a).

The greased internal part was inserted through the mold before pouring the mixture. Each sample was kept in the mold for 30 minutes; then, the specimen was removed from the mold and the internal part was pulled out of the specimen. The grease on the internal part prevented adhesion of the internal part to the sample, facilitating its removal. The internal blade left an open notch in the specimen through the thickness perpendicular to the front and back sides of the specimen. The opening of the notch was 1 mm. There was no evidence that pulling out the internal part produced any damage to the sample. After removal of the shim, the specimen was stored in a laboratory environment at a controlled temperature of $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 days. It is important to note that consistency in mixing, casting, curing, and testing was required to obtain acceptable test results.

Fig 2. (a) Mold for making CCHD specimens; (b) Mold used for making NBD specimens.

Concurrent with the preparation of the horseshoe-shaped specimen, nine NBD specimens were prepared for the purpose of comparison and validation of the CCHD results. Two semi-cylindrical molds were attached to each other by an elastic belt in preparation for the notched Brazilian disc (Fig 2b). The diameter and thickness of the mold were 90 and 27 mm, respectively. A metallic shim 40 mm in length was inserted in the middle of the mold, and the mixture then was poured into the mold. As the mixture hardened, the shim left an open notch in the specimen through its thickness perpendicular to the front and back of the specimen. Immediately after removing the shim, the front and back faces of the specimens were polished,

and the specimen was stored in the laboratory at a controlled temperature of $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 days.

2.2. Test set-up and loading

The CCHD specimen was placed on the wedge (Fig 3a); and vertical force was applied under load control by the testing system. Load and displacement data were recorded. Loading rates for rock fracture testing was $0.02 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m/s}}$ as followed by Barton 1983 (Barton 1983). The loading rate for the ISRM-recommended tests is not to be greater than $0.25 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m/s}}$ or such that failure occurs within 10 s (ISRM 1988). The loading rate, in terms of stress intensity, cannot be determined until after testing. In accordance with mode I fracture toughness testing, only the maximum load needs to be recorded for calculating the K_{Ic} .

2.3. Wedging device

The wedging device used to apply the splitting force along the crack mouth edge consisted of a granite wedge with a 28° angle, which is shown in Fig 3a.

Fig 3. (a) Experimental set up; (b) Free body diagram of the specimen on the wedge.

2.4. Stress Analysis

When the CCHD specimen was loaded by the wedge device, two normal (F_n) and shear (F_t) forces resulted from the vertical load on the specimen walls (Fig 3b). The horizontal force on the model walls were calculated as:

$$\vec{F}_H = \vec{F}_n + \vec{F}_t \quad (3)$$

where F_H is the resultant horizontal component of the force due to the combined effect of F_n and F_t acting on the wall. The relationship between F_n and F_t is:

$$\vec{F}_t = \mu \vec{F}_n \quad (4)$$

By considering forces equilibrium in the vertical, y, direction:

$$\sum Fy = 0 \quad (5)$$

i.e.

$$\frac{F_V}{2} - F_n \sin \theta - F_t \cos \theta = 0 \quad (6)$$

By substituting Eq (4) in Eq (6):

$$\frac{F_V}{2} - F_n \sin \theta - \mu F_n \cos \theta = 0 \quad (7)$$

Solving Eq (7) for F_n :

$$\frac{F_V}{2} - F_n (\sin \theta - \mu \cos \theta) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$F_n = \frac{F_V}{2 (\sin \theta + \mu \cos \theta)} \quad (9)$$

Considering the horizontal components of F_n and F_t , the horizontal force, F_H , Eq. (3) was rewritten as:

$$F_H = F_n \cos \theta - F_t \sin \theta \quad (10)$$

By substituting Eq (4) in Eq (10):

$$F_H = F_n \cos \theta - \mu F_n \sin \theta \quad (11)$$

and

$$F_H = F_n (\cos \theta - \mu \sin \theta) \quad (12)$$

By substituting Eq (9) in Eq (12):

$$F_H = \frac{F_V (\cos \theta - \mu \sin \theta)}{2 (\mu \cos \theta + \sin \theta)} \quad (13)$$

This horizontal force is shown in Fig 4.

Fig 4. Resultant F_H

The two acting horizontal forces on the specimen resulted in a moment acting along the plane of failure as shown in Fig 5.

Fig 5. Moment acting on the fracture plane

$$M = d \times F_H \quad (15)$$

Where F_H is the resultant horizontal force and d is the vertical distance between the point of application of the load and the neutral axis ~~the tip of the flaw~~. d in Fig 4 is equal to:

$$d = b + r_i + \left(\frac{r_o + r_i}{2} \right) \cos \theta + \left(\frac{r_o - r_i - b}{2} \right) \quad (16)$$

or

$$d = \frac{(b + r_o + r_i + (r_o + r_i) \cos \theta)}{2} \quad (17)$$

By substituting Eqs (14) and (17) in Eq (15):

$$M = \frac{(b + r_o + r_i + (r_o + r_i)\cos\theta)}{2} \times \frac{F_V(\cos\theta - \mu\sin\theta)}{2(\mu\cos\theta + \sin\theta)} \quad (18)$$

The maximum tensile stress force at the crack tip was calculated by:

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{Mc}{I} \quad (19)$$

Where M is the moment acting about the neutral axis of the intact area on the fracture plane and c is the maximum distance between the neutral axis and the crack tip (Fig 6). The neutral band goes through the rectangular section ahead of the notch tip (Fig 6). Based on the flexural stress theory, the neutral axis passes through the centroid of the cross section of the intact (unbroken) material. Because the failure surface is made of the same material, the neutral axis should pass through the geometric center of the failure surface, as indicated by the distance c from the tip in Fig. 6. I is the momentum of inertia which is calculated by the dimension of the rectangular section ahead of the notch tip (Fig 6).

Fig 6. Demonstration of acting moment on the fracture plane.

c and I were calculated as follows:

$$c = (r_o - r_i - b)/2 \quad (20)$$

$$I = \frac{t(r_o - r_i - b)^3}{12} \quad (21)$$

Where t is the specimen thickness. By substituting Eqs (18), (20), and (21) in Eq (19):

$$\sigma = \frac{\left(\frac{(b+r_o+r_i+(r_o+r_i)\cos\theta)}{2}\right) \times \left(\frac{F_V(\cos\theta-\mu\sin\theta)}{2(\mu\cos\theta+\sin\theta)}\right) \times ((r_o-r_i-b)/2)}{\left(\frac{t(r_o-r_i-b)^3}{12}\right)} \quad (22)$$

And finally

$$\sigma = \frac{3(b+r_o+r_i+(r_o+r_i)\cos\theta) \times (F_V(\cos\theta-\mu\sin\theta))}{2t(r_o-r_i-b)^2 \times (\mu\cos\theta+\sin\theta)} \quad (23)$$

A material's resistance to crack propagation can be quantified using fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , the critical stress intensity factor. When the stress intensity factor, K , at the crack tip reaches K_{Ic} , the fracture initiates and propagates until the stress intensity factor decreases below K_{Ic} . The stress intensity factor can be related to the applied stress (σ) and crack length (b) by the following generalized equation:

$$K_{Ic} = Y_I \sigma \sqrt{\pi b} \quad (24)$$

where Y_I is a dimensionless function dependent on the crack length, σ is the applied stress, and a is the half-crack length. Y_I is generally determined by finite element simulation by substituting Eq (23) in Eq (24):

$$K_{Ic} = Y_I \sqrt{\pi b} \times \frac{3(b+r_o+r_i+(r_o+r_i)\cos\theta) \times (F_V(\cos\theta-\mu\sin\theta))}{2t(r_o-r_i-b)^2 \times (\mu\cos\theta+\sin\theta)} \quad (25)$$

2.5. Modelling efforts to determine the dimensionless stress intensity factor (Y_I)

A new expression of the stress intensity factor was needed by the proposed method in order to determine the fracture toughness, which was developed using finite element analysis. A two-dimensional finite element code named FRANC2D/L (FRacture ANalysis Code for 2-D Layered structures) was used to do the numerical modeling work, assuming the plane strain condition. This code was originally developed at Cornell University and modified for multi-layers at Kansas State University, and is based on the theory of linear and nonlinear elastic fracture mechanics (Wawrzynek and Ingraffea 1991). The general methodology starts with the pre-processing stage, where the geometry, mesh, material properties, and boundary conditions are specified. The modeling continues with post-processing stage where loading conditions, crack definition and crack growth process are specified.

Fig 7a shows the finite mesh with the boundary and loading conditions. One individual node at the top of the model was fixed in the x direction. To obtain a detailed distribution of the induced stresses, up to 1,300 elements were used in the models. In the simulations, different $b/(r_o-r_i)$ ratios from 0.06 to 0.4 were considered where a is the crack length, R_o is the external radius of the disc, R_i is internal radius of hole ($r_o=45$ mm and $r_i=10$ mm), and a is the crack length ($b=9$ mm). These models were subjected to a compressive force, F_v , of 100 KN. The analyses were made on isotropic and linearly elastic materials. Fig 7b shows the deformed mesh after loading. This numerical technique has also been used by the authors and resulted in close prediction of fracture toughness values for the NBD specimen.

Fig 7. Finite element mesh for the proposed specimen: a) original mesh; b) deformed mesh.

The stress intensity factors obtained from the FEM analysis for different ratios of $b/(r_o-r_i)$ are presented in Table 2. The stress intensity factors were normalized with regard to the crack length (b) and the far field nominal stress (σ). The normalized stress intensity factor, Y_I , is determined from Eq. (24) as follows:

$$Y_I = \frac{K_I}{\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}} \quad (26)$$

Table 2. Ratios of $b/(r_o-r_i)$, stress intensity factor (K_I), and dimensionless shape function Y_I .

$b/(r_o-r_i)$	$K_I (MPa\sqrt{m})$	$\sigma\sqrt{\pi a} (MPa\sqrt{m})$	Y_I
0.06	0.358	0.063	5.68
0.07	0.389	0.072	5.4
0.08	0.435	0.083	5.24
0.10	0.512	0.099	5.17
0.12	0.653	0.122	5.35
0.16	0.977	0.159	6.14
0.26	2	0.226	8.84
0.4	6	0.396	15.15

The function of Y_I is determined by curve fitting of the normalized stress intensity factors with respect to the ratio of $b/(r_o-r_i)$. The third order polynomial was used to fit the normalized stress intensity factors in this study. Fig 8 demonstrates the variation of the function Y_I with respect to $b/(r_o-r_i)$.

$$Y_I = - 198.4 (b/(r_o-r_i))^3 + 223.8 (b/(r_o-r_i))^2 - 37.47 (b/(r_o-r_i)) + 7.014 \quad (27)$$

Fig 8. Variation of the function Y_I with respect to $b/(r_o-r_i)$.

2.6. Experimental Measurement of K_{Ic}

The calculation of fracture toughness using the CCHD test is straightforward. The fracture toughness can be calculated using Eq (26) by substituting F_v , r_i , r_o , θ , b , and μ . In order to determine rock fracture toughness, the coefficient of friction needs to be determined. A tilt test can be used to determine μ . The coefficients of friction between the three rock-like mixes used in this study and the granite wedge are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Values of friction and tilt angle from the tilt tests of roc-like materials on a hardened steel

Rock-like material	1	2	3
μ (tilt angle)	0.34 (19°)	0.33 (18°)	0.31 (17°)

3. Experimental Results

3.1 Failure Pattern in CCHD Test

Fig 9 shows the failure patterns observed in three different rock-like specimens. In all cases, the failure surface was tensile because it had a varnished finish, and no pulverized material or trace of shear displacement were observed. The tensile cracks initiated from the tip of the flaws and propagated parallel to the loading axis until they coalesced with the top edge of the specimen.

Fig 9. Failure pattern in (a) mix type I, (b) mix type II, and (c) mix type III.

3.2 Failure pattern in NBD test

Fig 10 shows the failure patterns observed in the same specimens tested using the NBD method. In all the tested specimens, the failure surface was tensile because no trace of shear displacement was observed.

Fig 10. Failure pattern in NBD specimens: (a) mix type I, (b) mix type II, (c) mix type III.

3.3. Fracture toughness values

Table 4 shows the results of the CCHD wedge splitting and the NBD tests. The results for each individual rock-like type indicated that the mean values of fracture toughness from both tests are different. In CCHD tests, pure tensile stress exists at the tip of the notch but an indirect tensile stress is distributed at tip of the notch in NBD tests. The discrepancy among the fracture toughness values obtained from specimens with different geometries is quite common and reported by previous studies (e.g., Cui et al. 2010, Keles and Tutluoglu 2011). We hypothesize that the amount of energy used for initiating the fracture in our CCHD test is less than the NBD test and therefore lower fracture toughness values are obtained for CCHD tests.

Table 4 Comparison of fracture toughness values from NBD test and CCHD test

Rock-like material	K_{IC} (MPa \sqrt{m})	
	CCHD	NBD
Mix 1	1.25	1.63
Mix 2	0.58	0.90
Mix 3	0.06	0.17

4. Fracture initiation and propagation modelling using PFC2D

PFC2D (Itasca 1999) is a discontinuous code that represents a rock mass as an assemblage of circular disks continued by planar walls. A 3-D version of the code is also available in which the particles are spheres; however, only 2-D models are discussed here. The distinct element method (Potyondy 1996, 2004) was used to model the forces and motions of the particles within the assembly. The particles move independently of one another and interact only at contacts. They are assumed to be rigid (non-deformable), but overlap can occur at the contacts. Contacts

are assumed to exist only at a point, not over some finite surface area as would be the case with fully deformable particles. The particles can be bonded together to simulate a comparable rock. The contact bonds can be considered as a pair of elastic springs (or a point of glue) with constant normal and shear stiffness acting at the point. The values assigned to them influence the macro deformation properties of the rock samples (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio). The contact bonds also have a specified shear and tensile strength. The values assigned to these strengths influence the macro strength of the sample and the nature of the cracking and failure that occurs during loading. The contact bonds allow tension to exist at the contacts until the force at the contact exceeds the strength of the bond, at which time the bond breaks and the tensile force becomes zero. Similarly, the contact can support shear forces until the bond breaks; but in this case, the shear force was set to a residual value that depends on the compressive normal force at the contact and the coefficient of friction. After a bond breaks in PFC2D, the stress is redistributed, which then may cause more cracks to form nearby. If the rock model is suitably stressed, then these bond breakages will localize into an inclined macro fracture that eventually causes sample failure. In this way, the deformation and fracture of rocks are modelled directly by allowing micromechanical damage to evolve, instead of indirectly by using constitutive equations as is the case in most continuum models. It has been shown that PFC can accurately reproduce the fundamental mechanical behavior of a range of rock types subjected to different stress regimes (Cundall 1979).

4.1 Model calibration

By using numerical simulation, the fracture toughness of type 2 specimens was determined. The Brazilian test was used to calibrate the tensile strength of the specimen in the PFC2D model. Adopting the micro-properties listed in Table 5 and the standard calibration procedures (Potyondy and Cundall 1996), a calibrated PFC particle assembly was created. The diameter of the Brazilian disk considered in the numerical tests was 54 mm. The specimen was made of 5615 particles. The disk was crushed as the lateral walls moved toward each other at a low speed of 0.016 m/s. The wall velocity was sufficiently low (0.016 m/s in all tests) to ensure a quasi-static equilibrium. Fig 11a, b illustrate the failure patterns observed in the experiments and numerical models, respectively. The failure planes experienced in the numerical and laboratory tests matched well. The numerical tensile strength and a comparison of its experimental measurements are also presented in Table 6. This table shows a good accord between the numerical and experimental results.

Table 5. Micro-properties used to represent the rock

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Type of particle	disc	Parallel bond radius multiplier	1
density	3000	Young modulus of parallel bond (GPa)	40
Minimum radius	0.27	Parallel bond stiffness ratio	1.7
Size ratio	1.56	Particle friction coefficient	0.4
Porosity ratio	0.08	Parallel bond normal strength, mean (MPa)	8
Damping coefficient	0.7	Parallel bond normal strength, SD (MPa)	2
Contact young modulus (GPa)	40	Parallel bond shear strength, mean (MPa)	8
Stiffness ratio	1.7	Parallel bond shear strength, SD (MPa)	2

Fig 11 a) failure pattern in a) physical sample, b) PFC2D model.

Table 6. Brazilian tensile strength of physical and numerical samples.

Physical tensile strength (MPa)	1.6
Numerical tensile strength (MPa)	1.7

The same PFC2D code was also used for simulation of fracture (crack) initiation and propagation in beam specimens subjected to 3-point bending (combination of shear and bending). Although the PFC2D calibration was done for the Brazilian specimen excellent agreement between the laboratory results and numerical simulations were observed by the authors for beam specimens.

4.2 CCHD Test Simulation

The CCHD test was simulated by creating a disc model in PFC2D using the calibrated micro-parameters (Fig 12). The diameter of the disk was 90 mm, and a 20mm diameter circle was removed. One semi-cone with a wall angle of 14° was also removed from the model to simulate the contact with the wedge. One 9 mm long notch was cut, and a 1mm opening was created in the upper portion of the disk. The specimen was made of 9,845 particles. One V-shaped loading wall was installed in the cone and two horizontal loading walls were installed in the upper side of the model and the lower side of the V-shaped wall. The disk was crushed as the horizontal walls moved toward each other at a low speed of 0.016 m/s. The crack initiation force was registered by taking the reaction forces on the horizontal wall (Fig 12).

Fig 12. CCHD test geometry

4.3. Tensile failure mechanism

a) Parallel Bond Forces in the Models before Crack Initiation

Fig 13a shows the parallel bond force distribution before the crack initiation in the PFC sample. The dark and red lines represent the compression and tensile forces in the model, respectively. The coarser the line is, the larger the force. As can be seen, the maximum force concentrations occurred around the notch tips, which means that the crack initiated at the tip of the notch. Also, the distribution of the forces on the fracture plane prior to fracturing confirms that the moment caused the top half of the fracture plane to experience compression and the bottom half to experience tension.

Fig 13. (a) The distribution of the parallel bond forces in the models before the crack initiation occurred and (b) propagation of cracks.

b) Failure patterns in numerical models

Fig 13b shows the progress of cracks in the CCHD specimen. The black lines and red lines represent the tensile cracks and shear cracks, respectively. Fig 13b shows that the tensile cracks initiated from the notch tips and propagated parallel to the loading axis until they coalesced with the sample edge.

5. Conclusions

- The CCHD test is capable of producing fracture toughness values that can be used to assess the relative fracture properties of different rock-like specimens.
- Using the CCHD test, one sample can be prepared within 30 minutes.
- A simple wedge is used to apply the splitting force along the crack mouth. The wedge provides a mechanical advantage as only a small vertical force needs to be applied to propagate the crack. A tilt test can be used to determine the coefficient of friction between the tested rock-like specimen and the wedge material.
- Finite element analysis renders the proper criteria for determination of the mode I fracture toughness.

- Determination of fracture toughness requires only the notch length and the critical applied load.
- Three different rock-like types were tested for fracture toughness using the CCHD test. These rock-like models were tested using a common fracture toughness test, the Notched Brazilian Disc test, which provided a basis for comparison. Repeatable values of fracture toughness were obtained for each rock-like material, which proves that the CCHD test can produce representative values.
- By using numerical modelling, the failure process was visually observed and the failure patterns were found to be reasonably close to the experimental results. Discrete element simulations demonstrated that the macro fractures in the models were caused by microscopic tensile breakages on a large numbers of bonded discs. In conclusion, the HCCD test can provide a representative toughness values using a simple, core- based specimen, requiring only an internal hole, a semi-cone with a wall angle of 14° , a straight notch, and straightforward data collection in order to determine K_{Ic} .

References (no need to edit)

- Atkinson C, Smelser RE, Sanchez J (1982) Combined mode fracture via the cracked Brazilian disk test. *Int J Fract* 18(4):279–291.
- Awaji H, Sato S (1978) Combined mode fracture toughness measurement by disk test. *J Eng Mater Technol* 100(2):175–182.
- Amrollahi H, Baghbanan A, Hashemolhosseini H (2011) Measuring fracture toughness of crystalline marbles under modes I and II and mixed mode I-II loading conditions using CCNBD and HCCD specimens. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 48(7):1123–1134.
- Ayatollahi MR, Alborzi MJ (2013) Rock fracture toughness testing using SCB specimen. In: 13th International Conference on Fracture. Beijing, China. 16–21 June; pp 1–7.
- Aliha MRM, Ayatollahi MR, Smith DJ, Pavier MJ (2010) Geometry and size effects on fracture trajectory in a limestone rock under mixed mode loading. *Eng Fract Mech* 77(11): 2200–2212.
- Aliha MRM, Ayatollahi MR, Akbardoost J (2012a) Typical upper bound-lower bound mixed mode fracture resistance envelopes for rock material. *Rock Mech Rock Eng* 45(1):65–74.
- Aliha MRM, Sistaninia M, Smith DJ, Pavier MJ, Ayatollahi MR (2012b) Geometry effects and statistical analysis of mode I fracture in guiting limestone. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 51:128–135.
- Anderson TL (2005) *Fracture mechanics: fundamentals and applications*. CRC Taylor & Francis, New York.
- Barton CC (1983) Variables in fracture energy, toughness of Rock. In: *Proceedings of the 24th US Symposium On Rock Mechanics*, Berkely, CA, p. 449–62.
- Bergmann G, Vehoff H (1994) Precracking of Nial singlecrystals by compression-compression fatigue and its application to fracture-toughness testing. *Scr Metall Mater* 30(8):969–974.
- Chang SH, Lee CI, Jeon S (2002) Measurement of rock fracture toughness under modes I and II and mixed-mode conditions by using disc-type specimens. *Eng Geol* 66(1):79–97.
- Chen CH, Chen CS, Wu JH (2008) Fracture toughness analysis on cracked ring disks of anisotropic rock. *Rock Mech Rock Eng* 41(4):539–562.
- Cui ZD, Liu DA, An GM, Sun B, Zhou M, Cao FQ (2010) A comparison of two ISRM suggested chevron notched specimens for testing mode-I rock fracture toughness. *Int J rock Mech Min Sci* 47:871–876.

- Cundall PA, Strack O. (1979) A discrete element model for granular assemblies. *Geotechnique*;29:47-65.
- Dai F, Chen R, Iqbal MJ, Xia K (2010a) Dynamic cracked chevron notched Brazilian disc method for measuring rock fracture parameters. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 47(4):606–613.
- Dai F, Chen R, Xia K (2010b) A semi-circular bend technique for determining dynamic fracture toughness. *Exp Mech* 50(6):783–791.
- Dai F, Xia K (2013) Laboratory measurements of the rate dependence of the fracture toughness anisotropy of Barre granite. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 60:57–65.
- Dai F, Wei MD, Xu NW, Ma Y, Yang DS (2015a) Numerical assessment of the progressive rock fracture mechanism of cracked chevron notched Brazilian disc specimens. *Rock Mech Rock Eng* 48(2):463–479.
- Dai F, Wei MD, Xu NW, Zhao T, Xu Y (2015b) Numerical investigation of the progressive fracture mechanisms of four ISRM-suggested specimens for determining the mode I fracture toughness of rocks. *Comput Geotech* 69:424–441.
- Dai F, Xia K, Zheng H, Wang Y (2011) Determination of dynamic rock mode-I fracture parameters using cracked chevron notched semi-circular bend specimen. *Eng Fract Mech* 78(15):2633–2644.
- Dwivedi RD, Soni AK, Goel RK, Dube AK (2000) Fracture toughness of rocks under sub-zero temperature conditions. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 37:1267–1275
- Fowell RJ, Chen JF (1990) The third chevron-notch rock fracture specimen-the cracked chevron-notched Brazilian disk. In: *Proceedings 31st US Symposium Rock*. Balkema, Rotterdam, pp 295–302.
- Fowell RJ, Xu C, Dowd PA (2006) An update on the fracture toughness testing methods related to the cracked chevron- notched Brazilian disk (CCNBD) specimen. *Pure Appl Geophys* 163:1047–1057.
- Fowell RJ, Xu C (1994) The use of the cracked Brazilian disc geometry for rock fracture investigations. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci Geomech Abstr.* 31(6): 571–579.
- Gunsallus, K. L., Kulhawy, F. H. (1984): A comparative evaluation of rock strength measures. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci Geomech Abstr.* 21(5): 233–248.
- Guo H, Aziz NI, Schmidt LC (1993) Rock fracture toughness determination by the Brazilian test. *Eng Geol* 33(3):177–188.
- Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014a). Multi-modal monitoring of slip along frictional discontinuities. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 47(5), 1575-1587, doi: 10.1007/s00603-014-0588-7.
- Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014b). Detection and quantification of slip along non-uniform frictional discontinuities using digital image correlation. *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 37 (5), doi: 10.1520/GTJ20130141.
- Hedayat, A., Pyrak-Nolte, L and Bobet, A. (2014c). Precursors to shear failure of rock discontinuities. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 41, 5467-5475, doi: 10.1002/2014GL060848.
- Hedayat, A., and Walton, G. (2017). Laboratory determination of rock fracture shear stiffness using seismic wave propagation and digital image correlation. *Geotechnical Testing Journal*, 40(10), 92-106.
- Iqbal MJ, and Mohanty B (2007) Experimental calibration of isrm suggested fracture toughness measurement techniques in selected brittle rocks. *Rock Mech. Rock Eng.* 40 (5), 453–475.
- ISRM (1988) suggested methods for determining the fracture toughness of rocks, Ouchterlony, F, Coordinator. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci & Geomech Abstr* 25:73–96.
- ISRM (2007) The complete ISRM suggested methods for rock characterization, testing and monitoring: 1974–2006. In: Ulusay R, Hudson JA (eds) *Suggested methods prepared by the commission on testing methods, International Society for Rock Mechanics*, compilation arranged by the ISRM Turkish National Group. Kozan Ofset, Ankara

- Itasca PFC2D (1999) Particle Flow Code in 2 Dimensions, Theory and background. Itasca Consulting Group, Minneapolis, MN, pp 1–124.
- Keles C, Tutluoglu L (2011) Investigation of proper specimen geometry for mode I fracture toughness testing with flattened Brazilian disc method. *Int J Fract* 169(1):61–75.
- Kuruppu MD, Chong KP (2012) Fracture toughness testing of brittle materials using semi-circular bend (SCB) specimen. *Eng Fract Mech* 91:133–150.
- Kuruppu MD, Obara Y, Ayatollahi MR, Chong KP, Funatsu T (2014) ISRM-Suggested method for determining the mode I static fracture toughness using semi-circular bend specimen. *Rock Mech Rock Eng* 47(1):267–274.
- Kuruppu MD (1998) Stress intensity factors of chevron-notched semi-circular specimens. In: Basu et al. (eds) *Proceedings 3rd APCOM, the aust inst of min & met*. pp 111–112.
- Lim IL, Johnston IW, Choi SK (1994) Assessment of mixed-mode fracture toughness testing methods for rock. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci Geomech Abstr* 31(3):265–272.
- Nasseri MHB, Mohanty B, Young RP (2006) Fracture toughness measurements and acoustic emission activity in brittle rocks. *Pure appl Geophys* 163:917–945.
- Ouchterlony F (1982) A review of fracture toughness testing of rocks. *Solid Mech Arch* 7:131–211.
- Ouchterlony F (1988) ISRM commission on testing methods. Suggested methods for determining fracture toughness of rock. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci Geomech Abstr* 25:71–96.
- Potyondy DO, Cundall PA (2004) A bonded-particle model for rock, *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 41 1329–1364.
- Potyondy DO, Cundall PA, Lee C (1996) Modeling of rock using bonded assemblies of circular particles. In: Aubertin M editor. *Proc. Second North American Rock Mechanics Symposium D NARMS '96, Montreal*. Rotterdam: Balkema. pp. 1934–44.
- Suresh S, Ewart L, Maden M, Slaughter WS, Nguyen M (1987) Fracture toughness measurements in ceramics-pre-cracking in cyclic compression. *J Mater Sci* 22(4):1271–1276.
- Shiryayev AM, Kotkis AM (1982) Methods for determining fracture-toughness of brittle porous materials. *Ind Lab* 48(9):917–918.
- Swan G, Alm O (1982) Sub-critical crack growth in Stripa granite: Direct observations. In: *Proc. 23rd. U. S. Symp. Rock Mech., University of California, Berkeley*, 542–550.
- Tang T, Bazant ZP, Yang S, Zollinger D (1996) Variable-notch one-size test method for fracture energy and process zone length. *Eng Fract Mech* 55(3):383–404.
- Thiercelin M, Roegiers JC (1986) Fracture toughness determination with the modified ring test. In: *Proceedings of the International Symposium On Engineering In Complex Rock Formations, Beijing, China*, pp 1–8.
- Tutluoglu L, Keles C (2011) Mode I fracture toughness determination with straight notched disk bending method. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 48(8):1248–1261.
- Thiercelin M (1989) Fracture toughness and hydraulic fracturing. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci Geomech Abstr* 26:177–183.
- Wang QZ, Xing L (1999) Determination of fracture toughness K_{Ic} by using the flattened Brazilian disc specimen for rocks. *Eng Fract Mech* 64(2):193–201.
- Wang QZ, Jia XM, Kou SQ, Zhang ZX, Lindqvist PA (2003) More accurate stress intensity factor derived by finite element analysis for the ISRM suggested rock fracture toughness specimen-CCNBD. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 4(2):233–241.
- Wawrzynek, P. A., and A. R. Ingraffea (1991) Discrete modelling of crack propagation: Theoretical aspects and implementation issues in two and three dimensions. *Rep. 91-5, Sch. of Civ. and Environ. Eng., Cornell Univ., Ithaca, N. Y.*
- Wei MD, Dai F, Xu NW, Xu Y, Xia K (2015) Three-dimensional numerical evaluation of the progressive fracture mechanism of cracked chevron notched semi-circular bend rock specimens. *Eng Fract Mech* 134:286–303.

- Xu NW, Dai F, Wei MD, Xu Y, Zhao T (2015) Numerical observation of three dimensional wing-cracking of cracked chevron notched Brazilian disc rock specimen subjected to mixed mode loading. *Rock Mech Rock Eng.* doi:10.1007/s00603-015-0736-8
- Yang S, Tang TX, Zollinger D, Gurjar A (1997) Splitting tension tests to determine rock fracture parameters by peak-load method. *Adv Cem Based Mater* 5:18–28.
- Zhou YX, Xia K, Li XB, Li HB, Ma GW, Zhao J, Zhou ZL, Dai F (2012) Suggested methods for determining the dynamic strength parameters and mode-I fracture toughness of rock materials. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 49:105–112.